

Linear Isometries on Pseudo-Euclidean Space (\mathbb{R}^n, μ)

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Abstract: A *pseudo-Euclidean space* (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) is such a Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n associated with a mapping $\mu : \vec{V}_{\bar{x}} \rightarrow \bar{x}\vec{V}$ for $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and a linear isometry $T : (\mathbb{R}^n, \mu) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^n, \mu)$ is such a linear isometry $T : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ that $T\mu = \mu T$. In this paper, we characterize curvature of s-line, particularly, Smarandachely embedded graphs and determine linear isometries on (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) .

Key Words: Smarandachely denied axiom, Smarandache geometry, s-line, pseudo-Euclidean space, isometry, Smarandachely map, Smarandachely embedded graph.

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§1. Introduction

As we known, a Smarandache geometry is defined following.

Definition 1.1 A rule $R \in \mathcal{R}$ in a mathematical system $(\Sigma; \mathcal{R})$ is said to be *Smarandachely denied* if it behaves in at least two different ways within the same set Σ , i.e., validated and invalidated, or only invalidated but in multiple distinct ways.

Definition 1.2 A *Smarandache geometry* is such a geometry in which there are at least one *Smarandachely denied ruler* and a *Smarandache manifold* $(M; \mathcal{A})$ is an n -dimensional manifold M that support a *Smarandache geometry* by *Smarandachely denied axioms* in \mathcal{A} . A line in a *Smarandache geometry* is called an *s-line*.

Applying the structure of a Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n , we are easily construct a special Smarandache geometry, called pseudo-Euclidean space([5]-[6]) following. Let $\mathbb{R}^n = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)\}$ be a Euclidean space of dimensional n with a normal basis $\bar{e}_1 = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$, $\bar{e}_2 = (0, 1, \dots, 0)$, \dots , $\bar{e}_n = (0, 0, \dots, 1)$, $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\vec{V}_{\bar{x}}$, $\bar{x}\vec{V}$ two vectors with end or initial point at \bar{x} , respectively. A *pseudo-Euclidean space* (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) is such a Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n associated with a mapping $\mu : \vec{V}_{\bar{x}} \rightarrow \bar{x}\vec{V}$ for $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, such as those shown in Fig.1,

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Fig.1

where $\vec{V}_{\bar{x}}$ and $\bar{x}\vec{V}$ are in the same orientation in case (a), but not in case (b). Such points in case (a) are called *Euclidean* and in case (b) *non-Euclidean*. A pseudo-Euclidean (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) is *finite* if it only has finite non-Euclidean points, otherwise, *infinite*.

By definition, a Smarandachely denied axiom $A \in \mathcal{A}$ can be considered as an action of A on subsets $S \subset M$, denoted by S^A . If $(M_1; \mathcal{A}_1)$ and $(M_2; \mathcal{A}_2)$ are two Smarandache manifolds, where $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2$ are the Smarandachely denied axioms on manifolds M_1 and M_2 , respectively. They are said to be *isomorphic* if there is 1-1 mappings $\tau : M_1 \rightarrow M_2$ and $\sigma : \mathcal{A}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_2$ such that $\tau(S^A) = \tau(S)^{\sigma(A)}$ for $\forall S \subset M_1$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}_1$. Such a pair (τ, σ) is called an isomorphism between $(M_1; \mathcal{A}_1)$ and $(M_2; \mathcal{A}_2)$. Particularly, if $M_1 = M_2 = M$ and $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}_2 = \mathcal{A}$, such an isomorphism (τ, σ) is called a *Smarandachely automorphism* of (M, \mathcal{A}) . Clearly, all such automorphisms of (M, \mathcal{A}) form a group under the composition operation on τ for a given σ . Denoted by $\text{Aut}(M, \mathcal{A})$. A special Smarandachely automorphism, i.e., linear isomorphism on a pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) is defined following.

Definition 1.3 Let (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) be a pseudo-Euclidean space with normal basis $\{\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_n\}$. A linear isometry $T : (\mathbb{R}^n, \mu) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^n, \mu)$ is such a transformation that

$$T(c_1\bar{e}_1 + c_2\bar{e}_2) = c_1T(\bar{e}_1) + c_2T(\bar{e}_2), \quad \langle T(\bar{e}_1), T(\bar{e}_2) \rangle = \langle \bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2 \rangle \quad \text{and} \quad T\mu = \mu T$$

for $\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2 \in \mathbf{E}$ and $c_1, c_2 \in \mathcal{F}$.

Denoted by $\text{Isom}(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu)$ the set of all linear isometries of (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) . Clearly, $\text{Isom}(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu)$ is a subgroup of $\text{Aut}(M, \mathcal{A})$.

By definition, determining automorphisms of a Smarandache geometry is dependent on the structure of manifold M and axioms \mathcal{A} . So it is hard in general even for a manifold. The main purpose of this paper is to determine linear isometries and characterize the behavior of s-lines, particularly, Smarandachely embedded graphs in pseudo-Euclidean spaces (\mathbb{R}^n, μ) . For terminologies and notations not defined in this paper, we follow references [1] for permutation group, [2]-[4] and [7]-[8] for graph, map and Smarandache geometry.

§2. Smarandachely Embedded Graphs in (\mathbb{R}^n, μ)

2.1 Smarandachely Planar Maps

Let L be an s-line in a Smarandache plane (\mathbf{R}^2, μ) with non-Euclidean points A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m for an integer $m \geq 0$. Its *curvature* $R(L)$ is defined by

$$R(L) = \sum_{i=1}^m (\pi - \mu(A_i)).$$

An s-line L is called *Euclidean* or *non-Euclidean* if $R(L) = \pm 2\pi$ or $\neq \pm 2\pi$. The following result characterizes s-lines on (\mathbb{R}^2, μ) .

Theorem 2.1 *An s-line without self-intersections is closed if and only if it is Euclidean.*

Proof Let (\mathbb{R}^2, μ) be a Smarandache plane and let L be a closed s-line without self-intersections on (\mathbb{R}^2, μ) with vertices A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m . From the Euclid geometry on plane, we know that the angle sum of an m -polygon is $(m-2)\pi$. Whence, the curvature $R(L)$ of s-line L is $\pm 2\pi$ by definition, i.e., L is Euclidean.

Now if an s-line L is Euclidean, then $R(L) = \pm 2\pi$ by definition. Thus there exist non-Euclidean points B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^m (\pi - \mu(B_i)) = \pm 2\pi.$$

Whence, L is nothing but an n -polygon with vertices B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m on \mathbb{R}^2 . Therefore, L is closed without self-intersection. \square

A planar map is a 2-cell embedding of a graph G on Euclidean plane \mathbb{R}^2 . It is called *Smarandachely* on (\mathbb{R}^2, μ) if all of its vertices are elliptic (hyperbolic). Notice that these pendent vertices is not important because it can be always Euclidean or non-Euclidean. We concentrate our attention to non-separated maps. Such maps always exist circuit-decompositions. The following result characterizes Smarandachely planar maps.

Theorem 2.2 *A non-separated planar map M is Smarandachely if and only if there exist a directed circuit-decomposition*

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(M) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s E(\vec{C}_i)$$

of M such that one of the linear systems of equations

$$\sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) = 2\pi, \quad \text{or} \quad \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) = -2\pi, \quad 1 \leq i \leq s$$

is solvable, where $E_{\frac{1}{2}}(M)$ denotes the set of semi-arcs of M .

Proof If M is Smarandachely, then each vertex $v \in V(M)$ is non-Euclidean, i.e., $\mu(v) \neq \pi$. Whence, there exists a directed circuit-decomposition

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(M) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s E(\vec{C}_i)$$

of semi-arcs in M such that each of them is an s-line in (\mathbb{R}^2, μ) . Applying Theorem 9.3.5, we know that

$$\sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - \mu(v)) = 2\pi \quad \text{or} \quad \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - \mu(v)) = -2\pi$$

for each circuit C_i , $1 \leq i \leq s$. Thus one of the linear systems of equations

$$\sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) = 2\pi, \quad 1 \leq i \leq s \quad \text{or} \quad \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) = -2\pi, \quad 1 \leq i \leq s$$

is solvable.

Conversely, if one of the linear systems of equations

$$\sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) = 2\pi, \quad 1 \leq i \leq s \quad \text{or} \quad \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) = -2\pi, \quad 1 \leq i \leq s$$

is solvable, define a mapping $\mu : \mathbf{R}^2 \rightarrow [0, 4\pi)$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} x_v & \text{if } x = v \in V(M), \\ \pi & \text{if } x \notin v(M). \end{cases}$$

Then M is a Smarandachely map on (\mathbf{R}^2, μ) . This completes the proof. \square

In Fig.2, we present an example of a Smarandachely planar maps with μ defined by numbers on vertices.

Fig.2

Let $\omega_0 \in (0, \pi)$. An s-line L is called *non-Euclidean of type ω_0* if $R(L) = \pm 2\pi \pm \omega_0$. Similar to Theorem 2.2, we can get the following result.

Theorem 2.3 *A non-separated map M is Smarandachely if and only if there exist a directed circuit-decomposition*

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(M) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s E(\vec{C}_i)$$

of M into s-lines of type ω_0 , $\omega_0 \in (0, \pi)$ for integers $1 \leq i \leq s$ such that one of the linear

systems of equations

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) &= 2\pi - \omega_0, & 1 \leq i \leq s, \\ \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) &= -2\pi - \omega_0, & 1 \leq i \leq s, \\ \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) &= 2\pi + \omega_0, & 1 \leq i \leq s, \\ \sum_{v \in V(\vec{C}_i)} (\pi - x_v) &= -2\pi + \omega_0, & 1 \leq i \leq s \end{aligned}$$

is solvable.

2.2 Smarandachely Embedded Graphs in (\mathbb{R}^n, μ)

Generally, we define the *curvature* $R(L)$ of an s-line L passing through non-Euclidean points $\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_m \in \mathbf{R}^n$ for $m \geq 0$ in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) to be a matrix determined by

$$R(L) = \prod_{i=1}^m \mu(\bar{x}_i)$$

and *Euclidean* if $R(L) = I_{n \times n}$, otherwise, *non-Euclidean*. It is obvious that a point in a Euclidean space \mathbf{R}^n is indeed Euclidean by this definition. Furthermore, we immediately get the following result for Euclidean s-lines in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) .

Theorem 2.4 *Let (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) be a pseudo-Euclidean space and L an s-line in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) passing through non-Euclidean points $\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_m \in \mathbf{R}^n$. Then L is closed if and only if L is Euclidean.*

Proof If L is a closed s-line, then L is consisted of vectors $\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_1\bar{x}_2}, \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_2\bar{x}_3}, \dots, \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_n\bar{x}_1}$. By definition,

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i+1}\bar{x}_i}}{|\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i+1}\bar{x}_i}|} = \frac{\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i-1}\bar{x}_i}}{|\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i-1}\bar{x}_i}|} \mu(\bar{x}_i)$$

for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$, where $i+1 \equiv (\text{mod } m)$. Consequently,

$$\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_1\bar{x}_2} = \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_1\bar{x}_2} \prod_{i=1}^m \mu(\bar{x}_i).$$

Thus $\prod_{i=1}^m \mu(\bar{x}_i) = I_{n \times n}$, i.e., L is Euclidean.

Conversely, let L be Euclidean, i.e., $\prod_{i=1}^m \mu(\bar{x}_i) = I_{n \times n}$. By definition, we know that

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i+1}\bar{x}_i}}{|\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i+1}\bar{x}_i}|} = \frac{\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i-1}\bar{x}_i}}{|\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i-1}\bar{x}_i}|} \mu(\bar{x}_i), \quad \text{i.e.,} \quad \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i+1}\bar{x}_i} = \frac{|\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i+1}\bar{x}_i}|}{|\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i-1}\bar{x}_i}|} \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_{i-1}\bar{x}_i} \mu(\bar{x}_i)$$

for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$, where $i + 1 \equiv (\text{mod } m)$. Whence, if $\prod_{i=1}^m \mu(\bar{x}_i) = I_{n \times n}$, then there must be

$$\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_1 \bar{x}_2} = \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_1 \bar{x}_2} \prod_{i=1}^m \mu(\bar{x}_i).$$

Thus L consisted of vectors $\overrightarrow{\bar{x}_1 \bar{x}_2}, \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_2 \bar{x}_3}, \dots, \overrightarrow{\bar{x}_n \bar{x}_1}$ is a closed s-line in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . \square

Now we consider the pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbf{R}^2, μ) and find the rotation matrix $\mu(\bar{x})$ for points $\bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^2$. Let $\theta_{\bar{x}}$ be the angle from \bar{e}_1 to $\mu\bar{e}_1$. Then it is easily to know that

$$\mu(\bar{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{\bar{x}} & \sin \theta_{\bar{x}} \\ \sin \theta_{\bar{x}} & -\cos \theta_{\bar{x}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now if an s-line L passing through non-Euclidean points $\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_m \in \mathbf{R}^2$, then Theorem 2.4 implies that

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{\bar{x}_1} & \sin \theta_{\bar{x}_1} \\ \sin \theta_{\bar{x}_1} & -\cos \theta_{\bar{x}_1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{\bar{x}_2} & \sin \theta_{\bar{x}_2} \\ \sin \theta_{\bar{x}_2} & -\cos \theta_{\bar{x}_2} \end{pmatrix} \dots \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{\bar{x}_m} & \sin \theta_{\bar{x}_m} \\ \sin \theta_{\bar{x}_m} & -\cos \theta_{\bar{x}_m} \end{pmatrix} = I_{2 \times 2}.$$

Thus

$$\mu(\bar{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_{\bar{x}_1} + \theta_{\bar{x}_2} + \dots + \theta_{\bar{x}_m}) & \sin(\theta_{\bar{x}_1} + \theta_{\bar{x}_2} + \dots + \theta_{\bar{x}_m}) \\ \sin(\theta_{\bar{x}_1} + \theta_{\bar{x}_2} + \dots + \theta_{\bar{x}_m}) & \cos(\theta_{\bar{x}_1} + \theta_{\bar{x}_2} + \dots + \theta_{\bar{x}_m}) \end{pmatrix} = I_{2 \times 2}.$$

Whence, $\theta_{\bar{x}_1} + \theta_{\bar{x}_2} + \dots + \theta_{\bar{x}_m} = 2k\pi$ for an integer k . This fact is in agreement with that of Theorem 2.1, only with different disguises.

An *embedded graph* G on \mathbf{R}^n is a 1-1 mapping $\tau : G \rightarrow \mathbf{R}^n$ such that for $\forall e, e' \in E(G)$, $\tau(e)$ has no self-intersection and $\tau(e), \tau(e')$ maybe only intersect at their end points. Such an embedded graph G in \mathbf{R}^n is denoted by $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$. For example, the n -cube \mathcal{C}_n is such an embedded graph with vertex set $V(\mathcal{C}_n) = \{ (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \mid x_i = 0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n \}$ and two vertices (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and $(x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_n)$ are adjacent if and only if they are differ exactly in one entry. We present two n -cubes in Fig.3 for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$.

Fig.3

Similarly, an embedded graph $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ is called *Smarandachely* if there exists a pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) with a mapping $\mu : \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow [\bar{x}]$ such that all of its vertices are non-Euclidean points in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . Certainly, these vertices of valency 1 is not important for Smarandachely embedded graphs. We concentrate our attention on embedded 2-connected graphs.

Theorem 2.5 *An embedded 2-connected graph $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ is Smarandachely if and only if there is a mapping $\mu : \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow [\bar{x}]$ and a directed circuit-decomposition*

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s E(\vec{C}_i)$$

such that these matrix equations

$$\prod_{\bar{x} \in V(\vec{C}_i)} X_{\bar{x}} = I_{n \times n} \quad 1 \leq i \leq s$$

are solvable.

Proof By definition, if $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ is Smarandachely, then there exists a mapping $\mu : \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow [\bar{x}]$ on \mathbf{R}^n such that all vertices of $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ are non-Euclidean in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . Notice there are only two orientations on an edge in $E(G_{\mathbf{R}^n})$. Traveling on $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ beginning from any edge with one orientation, we get a closed s-line \vec{C} , i.e., a directed circuit. After we traveled all edges in $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ with the possible orientations, we get a directed circuit-decomposition

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s E(\vec{C}_i)$$

with an s-line \vec{C}_i for integers $1 \leq i \leq s$. Applying Theorem 2.4, we get

$$\prod_{\bar{x} \in V(\vec{C}_i)} \mu(\bar{x}) = I_{n \times n} \quad 1 \leq i \leq s.$$

Thus these equations

$$\prod_{\bar{x} \in V(\vec{C}_i)} X_{\bar{x}} = I_{n \times n} \quad 1 \leq i \leq s$$

have solutions $X_{\bar{x}} = \mu(\bar{x})$ for $\bar{x} \in V(\vec{C}_i)$.

Conversely, if these is a directed circuit-decomposition

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^s E(\vec{C}_i)$$

such that these matrix equations

$$\prod_{\bar{x} \in V(\vec{C}_i)} X_{\bar{x}} = I_{n \times n} \quad 1 \leq i \leq s$$

are solvable, let $X_{\bar{x}} = A_{\bar{x}}$ be such a solution for $\bar{x} \in V(\vec{C}_i)$, $1 \leq i \leq s$. Define a mapping $\mu : \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow [\bar{x}]$ on \mathbf{R}^n by

$$\mu(\bar{x}) = \begin{cases} A_{\bar{x}} & \text{if } \bar{x} \in V(G_{\mathbf{R}^n}), \\ I_{n \times n} & \text{if } \bar{x} \notin V(G_{\mathbf{R}^n}). \end{cases}$$

Then we get a Smarandachely embedded graph $G_{\mathbf{R}^n}$ in the pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) by Theorem 2.4. \square

§3. Linear Isometries on Pseudo-Euclidean Space

If all points in a pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) are Euclidean, i.e., the case (a) in Fig.1, then (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) is nothing but just the Euclidean space \mathbf{R}^n . The following results on linear isometries of Euclidean spaces are well-known.

Theorem 3.1 *Let \mathbf{E} be an n -dimensional Euclidean space with normal basis $\{\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_n\}$ and T a linear transformation on \mathbf{E} determined by $\bar{Y}^t = [a_{ij}]_{n \times n} \bar{X}^t$, where $\bar{X} = (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_n)$ and $\bar{Y} = (T(\bar{e}_1), T(\bar{e}_2), \dots, T(\bar{e}_n))$. Then T is a linear isometry on \mathbf{E} if and only if $[a_{ij}]_{n \times n}$ is an orthogonal matrix, i.e., $[a_{ij}]_{n \times n} [a_{ij}]_{n \times n}^t = I_{n \times n}$.*

Theorem 3.2 *An isometry on a Euclidean space \mathbf{E} is a composition of three elementary isometries on \mathbf{E} following:*

Translation $\mathbb{T}_{\bar{e}}$. *A mapping that moves every point (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) of \mathbf{E} by*

$$T_{\bar{e}} : (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow (x_1 + e_1, x_2 + e_2, \dots, x_n + e_n),$$

where $\bar{e} = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$.

Rotation $\mathbb{R}_{\bar{\phi}}$. *A mapping that moves every point of \mathbf{E} through a fixed angle about a fixed point. Similarly, taking the center O to be the origin of polar coordinates $(r, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_{n-1})$, a rotation $R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}} : \mathbf{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{E}$ is*

$$R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}} : (r, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_{n-1}) \rightarrow (r, \phi_1 + \theta_1, \phi_2 + \theta_2, \dots, \phi_{n-1} + \theta_{n-1}),$$

where θ_i is a constant angle, $\theta_i \in \mathbf{R} \pmod{2\pi}$ for integers $1 \leq i \leq n-1$.

Reflection \mathbb{F} . *A reflection F is a mapping that moves every point of \mathbf{E} to its mirror-image in a fixed Euclidean subspace E' of dimensional $n-1$, denoted by $F = F(E')$. Thus for a point P in \mathbf{E} , $F(P) = P$ if $P \in E'$, and if $P \notin E'$, then $F(P)$ is the unique point in \mathbf{E} such that E' is the perpendicular bisector of P and $F(P)$.*

Theorem 3.3 *An isometry \mathcal{I} on a Euclidean space \mathbf{E} is affine, i.e., determined by*

$$\bar{Y}^t = \lambda [a_{ij}]_{n \times n} \bar{X}^t + \bar{e},$$

where λ is a constant number, $[a_{ij}]_{n \times n}$ a orthogonal matrix and \bar{e} a constant vector in \mathbf{E} .

Notice that a vector \vec{V} can be uniquely determined by the basis of \mathbf{R}^n . For $\bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$, there are infinite orthogonal frames at point \bar{x} . Denoted by $\mathcal{O}_{\bar{x}}$ the set of all normal bases at

point \bar{x} . Then a *pseudo-Euclidean space* (\mathbf{R}, μ) is nothing but a Euclidean space \mathbf{R}^n associated with a linear mapping $\mu : \{\bar{\epsilon}_1, \bar{\epsilon}_2, \dots, \bar{\epsilon}_n\} \rightarrow \{\bar{\epsilon}'_1, \bar{\epsilon}'_2, \dots, \bar{\epsilon}'_n\} \in \mathcal{O}_{\bar{x}}$ such that $\mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1) = \bar{\epsilon}'_1$, $\mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2) = \bar{\epsilon}'_2, \dots, \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n) = \bar{\epsilon}'_n$ at point $\bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$. Thus if $\vec{V}_{\bar{x}} = c_1\bar{\epsilon}_1 + c_2\bar{\epsilon}_2 + \dots + c_n\bar{\epsilon}_n$, then $\mu(\bar{x}\vec{V}) = c_1\mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1) + c_2\mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2) + \dots + c_n\mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n) = c_1\bar{\epsilon}'_1 + c_2\bar{\epsilon}'_2 + \dots + c_n\bar{\epsilon}'_n$.

Without loss of generality, assume that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1) &= x_{11}\bar{\epsilon}_1 + x_{12}\bar{\epsilon}_2 + \dots + x_{1n}\bar{\epsilon}_n, \\ \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2) &= x_{21}\bar{\epsilon}_1 + x_{22}\bar{\epsilon}_2 + \dots + x_{2n}\bar{\epsilon}_n, \\ &\dots\dots\dots, \\ \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n) &= x_{n1}\bar{\epsilon}_1 + x_{n2}\bar{\epsilon}_2 + \dots + x_{nn}\bar{\epsilon}_n. \end{aligned}$$

Then we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(\bar{x}\vec{V}) &= (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)(\mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1), \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2), \dots, \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n))^t \\ &= (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{nn} \end{pmatrix} (\bar{\epsilon}_1, \bar{\epsilon}_2, \dots, \bar{\epsilon}_n)^t. \end{aligned}$$

Denoted by

$$[\bar{x}] = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{nn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1), \bar{\epsilon}_1 \rangle & \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1), \bar{\epsilon}_2 \rangle & \dots & \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_1), \bar{\epsilon}_n \rangle \\ \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2), \bar{\epsilon}_1 \rangle & \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2), \bar{\epsilon}_2 \rangle & \dots & \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_2), \bar{\epsilon}_n \rangle \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n), \bar{\epsilon}_1 \rangle & \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n), \bar{\epsilon}_2 \rangle & \dots & \langle \mu(\bar{\epsilon}_n), \bar{\epsilon}_n \rangle \end{pmatrix},$$

called the *rotation matrix* of \bar{x} in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . Then $\mu : \vec{V}_{\bar{x}} \rightarrow \bar{x}\vec{V}$ is determined by $\mu(\bar{x}) = [\bar{x}]$ for $\bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$. Furthermore, such an rotation matrix $[\bar{x}]$ is orthogonal for points $\bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$ by definition, i.e., $[\bar{x}][\bar{x}]^t = I_{n \times n}$. Particularly, if \bar{x} is Euclidean, then such an orientation matrix is nothing but $\mu(\bar{x}) = I_{n \times n}$. Summing up all these discussions, we know the following result.

Theorem 3.4 *If (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) is a pseudo-Euclidean space, then $\mu(\bar{x}) = [\bar{x}]$ is an $n \times n$ orthogonal matrix for $\forall \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$.*

By definition, we know that $\text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^n) = \langle \mathbb{T}_{\bar{e}}, \mathbb{R}_{\bar{e}}, \mathbb{F} \rangle$. An isometry τ of a pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) is an isometry on \mathbf{R}^n such that $\mu(\tau(\bar{x})) = \mu(\bar{x})$ for $\forall \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$. Clearly, all such isometries form a group $\text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^n, \mu)$ under composition operation with $\text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^n, \mu) \leq \text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^n)$. We determine isometries of pseudo-Euclidean spaces in this subsection.

Certainly, if $\mu(\bar{x})$ is a constant matrix $[c]$ for $\forall \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$, then all isometries on \mathbf{R}^n is also isometries on (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . Whence, we only discuss those cases with at least two values for $\mu : \bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n \rightarrow [\bar{x}]$ similar to that of (\mathbf{R}^2, μ) .

Translation. Let (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) be a pseudo-Euclidean space with an isometry of translation $T_{\bar{e}}$, where $\bar{e} = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$ and $P, Q \in (\mathbf{R}^n, \mu)$ a non-Euclidean point, a Euclidean point,

respectively. Then $\mu(T_{\bar{e}}^k(P)) = \mu(P)$, $\mu(T_{\bar{e}}^k(Q)) = \mu(Q)$ for any integer $k \geq 0$ by definition. Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} &P, T_{\bar{e}}(P), T_{\bar{e}}^2(P), \dots, T_{\bar{e}}^k(P), \dots, \\ &Q, T_{\bar{e}}(Q), T_{\bar{e}}^2(Q), \dots, T_{\bar{e}}^k(Q), \dots \end{aligned}$$

are respectively infinite non-Euclidean and Euclidean points. Thus there are no isometries of translations if (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) is finite.

In this case, if there are rotations $R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}$, then there must be $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1} \in \{0, \pi/2\}$ and if $\theta_i = \pi/2$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$, $\theta_i = 0$ if $i \geq l+1$, then $e_1 = e_2 = \dots = e_{l+1}$.

Rotation. Let (R^n, μ) be a pseudo-Euclidean space with an isometry of rotation $R_{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}$ and $P, Q \in (\mathbf{R}^n, \mu)$ a non-Euclidean point, a Euclidean point, respectively. Then

$$\mu(R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}(P)) = \mu(P), \quad \mu(R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}(Q)) = \mu(Q)$$

for any integer $k \geq 0$ by definition. Whence,

$$\begin{aligned} &P, R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}(P), R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}^2(P), \dots, R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}^k(P), \dots, \\ &Q, R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}(Q), R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}^2(Q), \dots, R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}^k(Q), \dots \end{aligned}$$

are respectively non-Euclidean and Euclidean points.

In this case, if there exists an integer k such that $\theta_i | 2k\pi$ for all integers $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, then the previous sequences is finite. Thus there are both finite and infinite pseudo-Euclidean space (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) in this case. But if there is an integer i_0 , $1 \leq i_0 \leq n-1$ such that $\theta_{i_0} \nmid 2k\pi$ for any integer k , then there must be either infinite non-Euclidean points or infinite Euclidean points. Thus there are isometries of rotations in a finite non-Euclidean space only if there exists an integer k such that $\theta_i | 2k\pi$ for all integers $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. Similarly, an isometry of translation exists in this case only if $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1} \in \{0, \pi/2\}$.

Reflection. By definition, a reflection F in a subspace E' of dimensional $n-1$ is an involution, i.e., $F^2 = \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{R}^n}$. Thus if (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) is a pseudo-Euclidean space with an isometry of reflection F in E' and $P, Q \in (\mathbf{R}^n, \mu)$ are respectively a non-Euclidean point and a Euclidean point. Then it is only need that $P, F(P)$ are non-Euclidean points and $Q, F(Q)$ are Euclidean points. Therefore, a reflection F can be exists both in finite and infinite pseudo-Euclidean spaces (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) .

Summing up all these discussions, we get results following for finite or infinite pseudo-Euclidean spaces.

Theorem 3.5 *Let (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) be a finite pseudo-Euclidean space. Then there maybe isometries of translations $T_{\bar{e}}$, rotations $R_{\bar{\theta}}$ and reflections on (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . Furthermore,*

(1) *If there are both isometries $T_{\bar{e}}$ and $R_{\bar{\theta}}$, where $\bar{e} = (e_1, \dots, e_n)$ and $\bar{\theta} = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n-1})$, then $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1} \in \{0, \pi/2\}$ and if $\theta_i = \pi/2$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$, $\theta_i = 0$ if $i \geq l+1$, then $e_1 = e_2 = \dots = e_{l+1}$.*

(2) *If there is an isometry $R_{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1}}$, then there must be an integer k such that $\theta_i | 2k\pi$ for all integers $1 \leq i \leq n-1$.*

(3) There always exist isometries by putting Euclidean and non-Euclidean points $\bar{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$ with $\mu(\bar{x})$ constant on symmetric positions to E' in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) .

Theorem 3.6 Let (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) be a infinite pseudo-Euclidean space. Then there maybe isometries of translations $T_{\bar{e}}$, rotations $R_{\bar{\theta}}$ and reflections on (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) . Furthermore,

(1) There are both isometries $T_{\bar{e}}$ and $R_{\bar{\theta}}$ with $\bar{e} = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$ and $\bar{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1})$, only if $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n-1} \in \{0, \pi/2\}$ and if $\theta_i = \pi/2$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$, $\theta_i = 0$ if $i \geq l+1$, then $e_1 = e_2 = \dots = e_{l+1}$.

(2) There exist isometries of rotations and reflections by putting Euclidean and non-Euclidean points in the orbits $\bar{x}^{\langle R_{\bar{\theta}} \rangle}$ and $\bar{y}^{\langle F \rangle}$ with a constant $\mu(\bar{x})$ in (\mathbf{R}^n, μ) .

We determine isometries on (\mathbf{R}^3, μ) with a 3-cube \mathcal{C}^3 shown in Fig.9.4.2. Let $[\bar{a}]$ be an 3×3 orthogonal matrix, $[\bar{a}] \neq I_{3 \times 3}$ and let $\mu(x_1, x_2, x_3) = [\bar{a}]$ for $x_1, x_2, x_3 \in \{0, 1\}$, otherwise, $\mu(x_1, x_2, x_3) = I_{3 \times 3}$. Then its isometries consist of two types following:

Rotations:

R_1, R_2, R_3 : these rotations through $\pi/2$ about 3 axes joining centres of opposite faces;

$R_4, R_5, R_6, R_7, R_8, R_9$: these rotations through π about 6 axes joining midpoints of opposite edges;

$R_{10}, R_{11}, R_{12}, R_{13}$: these rotations through about 4 axes joining opposite vertices.

Reflection F : the reflection in the centre fixes each of the grand diagonal, reversing the orientations.

Then $\text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^3, \mu) = \langle R_i, F, 1 \leq i \leq 13 \rangle \simeq S_4 \times Z_2$. But if let $[\bar{b}]$ be another 3×3 orthogonal matrix, $[\bar{b}] \neq [\bar{a}]$ and define $\mu(x_1, x_2, x_3) = [\bar{a}]$ for $x_1 = 0, x_2, x_3 \in \{0, 1\}$, $\mu(x_1, x_2, x_3) = [\bar{b}]$ for $x_1 = 1, x_2, x_3 \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\mu(x_1, x_2, x_3) = I_{3 \times 3}$ otherwise. Then only the rotations R, R^2, R^3, R^4 through $\pi/2, \pi, 3\pi/2$ and 2π about the axis joining centres of opposite face

$$\{(0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 1), (0, 1, 0), (0, 1, 1)\} \text{ and } \{(1, 0, 0), (1, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (1, 1, 1)\},$$

and reflection F through to the plane passing midpoints of edges

$$(0, 0, 0) - (0, 0, 1), (0, 1, 0) - (0, 1, 1), (1, 0, 0) - (1, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0) - (1, 1, 1)$$

or $(0, 0, 0) - (0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 1) - (0, 1, 1), (1, 0, 0) - (1, 1, 0), (1, 0, 1) - (1, 1, 1)$

are isometries on (\mathbf{R}^3, μ) . Thus $\text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^3, \mu) = \langle R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4, F \rangle \simeq D_8$.

Furthermore, let $[\bar{a}_i], 1 \leq i \leq 8$ be orthogonal matrixes distinct two by two and define $\mu(0, 0, 0) = [\bar{a}_1], \mu(0, 0, 1) = [\bar{a}_2], \mu(0, 1, 0) = [\bar{a}_3], \mu(0, 1, 1) = [\bar{a}_4], \mu(1, 0, 0) = [\bar{a}_5], \mu(1, 0, 1) = [\bar{a}_6], \mu(1, 1, 0) = [\bar{a}_7], \mu(1, 1, 1) = [\bar{a}_8]$ and $\mu(x_1, x_2, x_3) = I_{3 \times 3}$ if $x_1, x_2, x_3 \neq 0$ or 1 . Then $\text{Isom}(\mathbf{R}^3, \mu)$ is nothing but a trivial group.

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